

ECOLOGICAL MODERNIZATION: A SOCIOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

Ecological modernization is an approach to address environmental problems that suggests ecological crisis can be resolved politically, economically and technologically in the context of existing institutions and power structures and continued economic growth. Political institutions and processes can be modernized in order to change the direction of the economy towards environmental improvement. It places considerable emphasis on the roles of technology, innovation and market dynamics as drivers for change. Ecological modernization is both a theory of, and a practical program for, change. Despite incorporation into policies in a number of nation states, ecological modernization has been criticised for its poor theorization of the state and power relations, as well as its co-option by vested interests.

Introduction

Ecological modernisation, also known as ‘Eco – restructuring’, emerged in the west in the mid 1950 due to increased ecological crisis developed side by side the growth in the economy.so ecological modernisation is a response to radical environmental movement that has development. Proponents of ecological modernisation theory believed that environmental reform could take place modernisation would lead to efficient use of natural resources and less emission of pollution.

A growing recognition that the result of human impacts upon the environment is a key challenge for global society has led to a number of responses from academics and policy makers alike. However, although there is broad agreement that the world is experiencing major environmental changes as a consequence, notably enhanced global warming and climatic change, there is much less agreement on how these problems should be tackled. There is a spectrum of opinions here, from that of deep green ecologists, who would advocate wholesale restructuring of the economy and society, through to some economists who see the market as being capable of restoring environmental equilibrium. One approach to addressing environmental problems which takes a position between these two is ecological modernization. Unlike the more radical green approaches, ecological modernization suggests that the ecological crisis can be reconciled with current forms of economic development and institutions to form a new mode of development for capitalist economies. However, in some versions it also sees a greater role for purposive intervention than just relying on market forces.

Ecological modernization privileges the role of technology, especially the role of innovation, and market dynamics as drivers for change. While these may have been the source of past environmental degradation it is argued that when directed towards solving environmental problems, innovation and markets can be combined with the modernization of political institutions and processes to steer a change towards environmental improvement. Ecological modernization frames environmental problems in such a way that they can be solved politically, economically and technologically in the context of existing institutions and power structures and continued economic growth. Ecological modernization frames environmental problems in such a way that they can be solved politically, economically and technologically in the context of existing institutions and power structures and continued economic growth. Ecological modernization, at least in some forms, appears to allow us to

have it all – not only does it deliver environmental improvement, but it also does so without seriously challenging existing economic practices. Indeed, ecological modernization suggests that addressing environmental problems can produce ‘win-win’ outcomes that increase firms’ profits, as well as an improved environment.

Ecological Modernization:

Ecological modernization concept was first developed in the 1980s by Joseph Huber (1982) and Martin Jänicke (1985). In Huber’s (1982, 1985) view, industrial society needed to experience a transition away from the current basis of industrial society towards a new relationship between economy and ecology to create a more ecologically rational organization of production. According to Huber-there is three phases of industrial society –1-Industrial break through, 2-Construction of industrial society,3-Ecological switchover. To understand modern society, Huber differentiates three analytical categories: - Industrial system,(techno sphere) life world (socio sphere) and nature (bio sphere).according to Huber is that the socio sphere and bio sphere are colonised by the techno sphere. according to him this fault in the ‘structural design’ can be overcome with ecological modernization. According to Arthur Mol, can be defined as the growing independence or autonomy of ecological perspective and consumption (Mol 2002: 93). In other words, it means the growing institutionalization of ecological rationality in the domain of economics (Mol 2002:109). According to F.H. Buttel, ecological modernization assumes that institutions are malleable and industrial capitalism has the technological capabilities to bring about “eco-efficiencies” or “improved” sustainable development (Buttel 2002: 63). According to Spaargaren and Mol, similar to the concept of “ecologisation of the economy” in the consumption cycles. It means putting economic value on nature, which forms the sustenance base of production and consumption (Spaargaren and Mol 1992:335).

Ecological modernization theory takes the ‘middle path’ between the neo-Marxist and neo-liberals. It is by first understanding the contributions of ecological modernization theorists that we will be able to appreciate how ecological modernization has progress in its theoretical formulation. According to neo-Marxist scholars, it is this unchecked global capitalism that ultimately destroy the sustenance base production and consumption (Mol 2002: 95). In other words globalization would end up destroying the economy order itself. According to neo-Marxist scholars, it is this unchecked global capitalism that will ultimately destroy the sustenance base of production and consumption (Mol 2002 : 95).In other words, globalization would end up destroying the capitalist economic order itself. The destruction of capitalist order due to the destruction of the sustenance base of production and consumption is known as the “ second contradiction of capitalism” .perhaps, this is one of the reason for the popularity of the treadmill of production theory. Mol attributed the popularity of the treadmill of production theory to the emergence of globalization (Mol 2002).

In recent years, Mol and Spaargaren have offered a revision of ecological modernization theory. They see the initial debates on environment and environmental sociology in the late 1970s and the early 1980s as an over-reaction to the dominant schools of thought led by neo- Marxist and counter productivity thinkers (Mol and Spaargaren, in Hannigan 2006).Initially, they challenge the neo-Marxist and counter – productivity thinkers, for claiming that modernization project was dying and its ecological deterioration could be salvage by recognizing the core institution of modern society like the economic market and industries. However, according to mol, this is no longer the case today’s capitalism has evolved in green direction. Today, capitalism is no longer seen as essential or an obstruction to radical environmental reform(Hanningan2006). Initially the neo- Marxists were seen as the rivals of ecological modernization theorist. Scholars observed that ecological modernization

theorist are now seen as making a theoretical alliance with the neo-Marxists against their common rivals –post modernists and social constructionist. the reason are not far to seek. According to Post-modernist Bluhdorn the idea of ecological rationality is about Power, politics and big money. Similarly, ecological modernization theory reject strong social constructionist because they believed that environmental problem has no real existence(Hanningan2006).Scholars of ecological theory see any changes in the institution and social practices, due to ecological interest in mind, as structural change.as result , advocated of treadmill of production theory are pessimistic of the future, whereas scholars of ecological modernization are optimistic of finding solutions to ecological problem(Buttel 2000).

Why ecological modernization has become popular, especially in the developed countries. There are different perspectives on ecological modernization.

F.H. Buttel has given us four views on ecological modernization ---

- The first view on ecological modernization known as ‘Objectivism’ in this perspectives contributed the most by Arthur Mol and Spaargaren from north America and Britain. the others are Germany and Netherland led by Joseph Huber and Martin Janicke.
- The second view is that of ‘Constructivism’. This view looks at ecological modernization as the dominant discourse of environmental policy in advanced countries. One of its proponents Hajer believes that ecological modernization may dilute the impulse for environmental reform, as it tends to obscure the role of capital, technology and consumer culture. for this reason, Hajer’s - idea is seen as hostile to ecological modernization.
- The third view is that of the environmental management, which is closely associated with industrial ecology and eco- restructuring in the private sector. Example is that of waste recycling which increase efficiency and minimizes pollution and waste (Buttel 2000).
- The fourth view on ecological modernization is associated with environmental policy innovation. Scholars like Murphy see the incorporation of environmental policy as an instant of ecological modernization (Murphy, in Buttel 2000).

Ecological modernization popularity has to do with its effective response to a variety of circumstances rather than theoretical clarity. First, ecological modernization was seen as a respond to the radical environment movement in northern Europe in the 1980s, which see globalization leading to environmental degradation. Second there was also a realization that sustainability and sustainable development has its own limitation, as it lacks guidance and vision for future environment policy (Buttel 2000). In fact, the concept of sustainability is more applicable to global South, which rely more on primary renewal sectors in rural areas. In other words in developed countries, ecological modernization was seen as an alternative to sustainability.

Ecological Modernization and the Global Economy attempts to understand environmental reform in the context of globalisation. Arthur Mol seems to suggest that ecological modernisation is the answer to environmental degradation. Let us try to examine some of his argument on how to tame the ill effect of global capitalism on environment and its consequences for ecological modernisation. For this, we will have to look at some of the actors, institutions and mechanisms that are emerging at the global level in the wake of global capitalism.

Arthur Mol suggested that one of the ways of taming global capitalism was through political modernisation. This he believes was taking shape through Multilateral Environmental Agreement (MEA) on issues like protection of ozone layer, oceans, etc. In fact, such MEAs were leading to a common denominator in terms of law and policy principle, which ultimately will lead to universal environmental law and policy (Mol 2002). Mol also argues that regional institution like European

Union (EU) has environmental protection as important component in its economic integration. This would serve a long way in coming up with global governance on environment. Further, Mol pointed out that supra-national institutions like the European Commission, European Parliament, and European Court of Justice could effectively counter environmental degradation where member state or transnational companies (TNCs) are directly a party to it.

According to Mol, market induced environmental reform can be carried out across the globe through the logic and rationality of the market. However, this does not mean that environmental innovation and reform originates in the economic domain. Market induced environmental reform, according to Mol, is the result of —political decision, civil pressures and citizen-consumer demand (Mol 2002). These are in the domains outside that of the market. One should note that environmental reform through the market is not permanent. Market induced environmental reform is still at its nascent stage. It still needs to be propelled by environmental institutions and environmental movement. Sometimes environmental reform becomes ambivalent because different economic actors have different economic interest. The problem gets accentuated when developed countries design environmental standards and underdeveloped countries are left out. It also gets accentuated when countries vied with each other for global capital. How then do we tame global capital? We know that global capital may be mobile but economic actors and mechanisms, which are part and parcel of markets, are localised.

This means that the material operation of global capital requires political legitimisation, both at the national and international level. In fact, market exists because of political legitimation and it is the material basis of its operation that allows the localisation of the market. It is this localised nature of the market, which permits environmental scrutiny (Mol 2002).

Ecological Modernization: A Critique

In recent years, environmentalism has become institutionalized – environmental agendas and objectives are part and parcel of most nation states' policies and major corporations devote space in their reports and on their websites to trumpet their contributions to sustainable development and corporate social responsibility. Although it is clear that institutional changes and environmental improvements have occurred and that the changes advocated by the proponents of ecological modernization are desirable, there are a number of problems with ecological modernization as a theory and as a policy program. First, one criticism of ecological modernization as both theory and discourse is that in its weak forms it can help to legitimate an environmental policy-making culture that absolves private-sector businesses and major corporations of their broader environmental responsibilities.

This is perhaps not surprising given its emphasis on technological innovation, creating markets for new goods and services and the role of large producers and retailers in developed economies as a force for change. Indeed, this may be one reason for its widespread popularity and some sectors of business have seen substantial profits to be made from improved environmental technologies and stricter global environmental regulation, for example in the emerging clean tech sectors. For the advanced capitalist nations, struggling to remain competitive against the rise of emerging economies in Asia, imposing strong environmental regulations which require high-tech solutions has provided not only a competitive advantage for their own domestic industries, but also a strong export market for these same environmental technologies. As a counter to this, developing economies have been critical of such initiatives, seeing these as a new form of protectionism and as 'environmental imperialism'. Thus while ecological modernization may be predicated upon the potential

transformation of capitalist economies, it is also liable, as a discourse, to be co-opted by powerful economic actors such that there is greater dominance of global resources by transnational industry, national governments, and 'big science'. Certainly the ecological modernization discourse has been incorporated into both corporate reporting and the agendas of global economic institutions without much apparent change to everyday practices.

The underlying conceptualizations of ecological modernization can therefore act to perpetuate the dominant forms of economic power. At the same time there is little recognition in ecological modernization approaches that some industries may find it impossible to innovate to reduce their impacts – it may be too expensive or technologically impossible to do so. In these cases, for example in the fossil fuel industries or the automotive industry, an alternative strategy may be to lobby for exemptions or attempt to dilute environmental policies. There are thus limits to the extent to which changes can be made within the modernization framework – not all sectors may be able or willing to make the shift. Moreover, other developments may represent a shift away from ecological modernization processes. For example, the increasing use of fracking for gas, especially in the USA, appears to be creating a new model for energy production, albeit aligned to the existing carbon-based system. The environmental impacts of this, both through increased carbon emissions and more localized concerns over water table pollution, are considerable.

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Second, despite a focus on the institutional reorganization of society, ecological modernization approaches often contain little detailed analysis of the forms of institutional adaptation or change that are required. It can be argued that this is a product of the under-theorization of the state in ecological modernization and oversimplifying assumptions about the role of states in ecological transformations. As was pointed out earlier, in Huber's work the role of the (central, regional, or local) state was seen as minimal. In later accounts, there has been a more sophisticated understanding that the state performs an enabling and contextually steering role. In this view, the enabling state will deliver ecological modernization through corporatist relationships between government and industry, although co-opting environmental movements when necessary. Certainly, many accounts have recognized the continued importance of the nation-state, albeit one that is no longer solely responsible (if it ever was) for environmental governance. This failure to adequately conceptualize the state and the social processes at work means that the type of embedded cultural transformations that will sustain factors, such as environmental improvements, reduced consumption, and greater equity, are unlikely to be realized. Third, ecological modernization lacks a theory of power relations. In some accounts, the assumption often appears to be that the logic of ecological modernization is so obvious (and profitable for business) that its widespread adoption is simply a matter of time as long as a mix of international civil society and environmental nongovernmental organizations keep up the pressure. In a situation where nobody seems to oppose it and where the theory lacks any scope to encompass power relations, there is little perceived room for opposition and ecological modernization is assumed to occur almost automatically. In other accounts, ecological modernization will only occur if there is sufficient societal, political, administrative, and organisational capacity. Even then, this needs to be accompanied by the presence of a range of variables, such as strong corporatist institutions, innovative legal and informational systems, and a proficient regulatory system.

The implementation of ecological modernization, as with any policy, however, is about the exercise of political and economic power, and although this is rarely made explicit, ecological modernization is a fundamentally political concept. Whether it can be successfully introduced depends upon

questions such as who is in control, who sets agendas, who allocates resources, who mediates disputes, and ultimately who sets the rules of the game. Ecological modernization is thus as much an ideological and political issue as it is an ecological and economic one. Indeed, ecological modernization has been criticised by both neo-Marxist and deep green critics who argue that the current capitalist system is inherently unable to reform itself along ecological lines beyond a weak 'light-green' reform programme of 'green washing' and that more fundamental structural changes are needed in the economy and society. In the process, the logics of neo-liberalism and ecological modernisation are said to have depoliticised environmental policy through scientific and econocentric discourses to exclude the consideration of alternative strategies. Certainly advocates of ecological modernization have had little to say about the impact of neo-liberal economic policies upon the environment, nor about the ability of markets to resolve environmental crisis. Such a critique would suggest that ecological modernization needs a more radical edge to it if it is to lead to any substantive changes. This would require addressing the key underlying processes at work, including the associated power structures, social relations, institutional configurations, discourses and belief systems, that currently lead to environmental and social injustice. However, ecological modernization is not (yet, at least) a distinct social theory; to become so, it needs to adequately incorporate theories of politics and the state.

Buttel critiques ecological modernization theory as not well-development social theory as it is shaped by broader political and economic factors. he also criticises ecological modernization theory as an indistinct social theory because the logic of ecological modernization is dependent upon political processes and practices (Buttel 2000). one weaknesses of ecological modernization, as pointed out by Buttel, is Eurocentric perspective, where the theoretical roots and empirical examples are derived mainly from North European countries. The other criticism against ecological modernization theory, according to Hannigan , is its unflappable technological optimism. Ecological modernisation theory 'super – industrialization'. In other words, whatever change or environment improvement look place was because of selective sampling and may not give the true picture of the industries. It means that claim of ecological improvement are made through fudging or manipulating of data.

Conclusion:

In this paper tried to understand ecological modernization. Then examined the contributions of various ecological modernisation theorists and the revision that has taken place in ecological modernisation theory. Next in this paper explored the different perspectives on ecological modernisation and also tried to explain the reasons behind the popularity of ecological modernisation.

This paper explained the conditions of ecological modernization under globalization. Here examined how various stake holder could bring institutional changes, which would mitigate the ill effect of global capitalism. Lastly in this paper indicated some of the criticism on the ecological modernization.

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